

Health Data Sharing is Caring

Natalia Norori - @natalianorori - natalianorori@gmail.com

Stefano Vrizzi - @stefanovrizzi - svrizzi@posteo.net

Get the slides: bit.ly/healthmozfest19

AI has introduced the possibility of using aggregated healthcare data to produce powerful models that can automate diagnosis.

Scientists often lack access to balanced datasets needed to optimally train algorithms.

Skin Cancer: Malignant vs. Benign

Download the dataset at bit.ly/kaggle2

<https://github.com/stefanovrizzi/healthdata/>

Early Biomarkers of Parkinson's Disease

Early biomarkers of Parkinson's disease based on natural connected speech

Download the dataset at bit.ly/kaggle1

dataset.csv (29.72 KB)		20 of 65 columns ▾		View
	A Participant code ▾	# Age (years) ▾	A Gender ▾	
	130 unique values		M 79% F 21%	

Diabetes 130 US hospitals for years 1999-2008

Diabetes - readmission

Download the dataset at bit.ly/kaggle3

A race	▼	A gender	▼	A age	▼
Caucasian	75%	Female	54%	[70-80)	26%
AfricanAmerican	19%	Male	46%	[60-70)	22%
Other (4)	6%	Other (1)	0%	Other (8)	52%

Heart Disease UCI

Download the dataset at bit.ly/kaggle4

Why is this happening?

How might we help reduce data imbalances ?

Sources

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Session outcomes and post
its

Can we improve the underlying data for our AI?

Yes.

True

What is the benefit "requirements are listening. the risks?"

↑

AI HAS INTRODUCED THE POSSIBILITY OF USING HEALTHCARE DATA TO PRODUCE POWERFUL MODELS THAT CAN AUTOMATE DIAGNOSIS.

SCIENTISTS OFTEN LACK ACCESS TO BALANCED DATA SETS. NEEDED TO OPTIMALLY TRAIN ALGORITHMS AND AVOID REPLICATING BIAS.

What is a balanced data set?

↑

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Data maintenance will require more pp!

True
Responsible
Data Governance
- RRI needed
Measure enough?
(Trustworthiness of AI?) +1

↑

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Identity or Bias?

Will skin color change the prediction?

ML needs to be maintained as per the progress

You can't argue against the potentials of ML; we wait for realities

either/or but a spectrum of development?

True
Geburu Karanami (2018)

How do we promote/encourage diversity of data?

So how do we get more diversity without the Pitfalls?

We need more data to train algorithms!
+ Need greater feedback loops!

MACHINE LEARNING HAS THE POTENTIAL TO SAVE THOUSANDS OF PEOPLE FROM SKIN CANCER EACH YEAR.

MOST PROGRAMS ARE LEARNING ON LIGHT SKIN, AND MAY UNDERPERFORM ON IMAGES OF LESIONS IN SKIN OF COLOR.

TAKE THE RED

HEALTH DIVERSITY

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THE FRAMINGHAM RISK SCORE PREDICTS THE RISK FOR FUTURE CORONARY HEART DISEASE EVENTS.

THE FRAMINGHAM RISK SCORE ONLY WORKS IN A SPECIFIC COHORT OF PEOPLE.

TAKE THE RED PILL. LET'S FIGHT FOR BETTER HEALTH DATA. IS CARING FOR YOURSELF WORTH IT?

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Should be true to the AI identify heart disease early

Still valuable for that group

Let's use a new risk score?

But we have learned a lot from this study affecting population health

Highlights of bias against blacks, women etc

PUBLICLY AVAILABLE GENOMIC DATA ALLOWS RESEARCHERS FROM ALL OVER THE WORLD TO STUDY DISEASES AND ADVANCE SCIENCE.

81% OF PARTICIPANTS IN GENOME MAPPING STUDIES ARE OF EUROPEAN ANCESTRY.

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How do we build systems that encourage diverse research?

Not surprising!

Why?

Workspace must be changed

True! And what about private companies?

But is this sharing free of risks?

WHAT IS THE IMPACT ON PRIVACY?

Makes a lot of sense. That is where money is.

Really? this is really bad. How can we be going to treat our population?

Conclusions inform policies which can entrench biases

ASSOCIATED DATA LINKS MUST BE CAREFULLY ANALYZED

DEPENDS ON THE RESEARCH.

THIS SOUNDS GREAT IN THEORY AS LONG AS FEEDBACK LOOPS ARE USED. +1

IS THIS AN HEALTH VERSION OF 'MINORITY REPORT'?

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A STUDY THAT TRACKED CANCER MORTALITY RATES IN THE U.S. HELPS PUBLIC HEALTH AUTHORITIES IDENTIFY POPULATIONS AT RISK.

LACK OF DIVERSE RESEARCH SUBJECTS IS A KEY REASON WHY THE STUDY PREDICTS THAT BLACK AND HISPANIC PEOPLE ARE MORE LIKELY TO DIE FROM CANCER THAN THEY REALLY ARE.

HOW MIGHT WE VALIDATE?

ASK TO STOP SMOKING KATATA.

Bias

Bias in DATA SETS ARE a PROBLEM

IS bias not explicit in the research outputs?

THE USE OF DISEASE VEILLANCE DATA HAS BECOME CRUCIAL FOR PUBLIC HEALTH ACTION AGAINST NEW THREATS, INCLUDING DENGUE AND ZIKA.

THE POTENTIAL BIASES AND LACK OF COMPARABILITY ACROSS COUNTRIES ARE LIMITING THE EFFICIENT USE OF THE DATA.

RED PILL. LET'S FIX REAL HEALTH DATA. WE ARE CARING

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AT WHAT EXPENSE?

DATA CAN BE MISUSED

CON DO! Requires responsible data governance principles/legislation - Global

DATA MANAGEMENT AND SHARING IT IS NOT EASY. HUMAN RESOURCE INFRASTRUCTURES.

NEED GLOBAL, OPEN INFRASTRUCTURE

!!!

THAT'S THE DIFFERENCE BETWEEN ROCK AND A HARD PLACE

TRUE IF IT HAPPENS NOT OFTEN

SOUNDS IMPORTANT TO FOCUS ON. ESPECIALLY IN COUNTRIES WITH LIMITED DATA.

SURVEILLANCE DATA ABOUT PERSONS OR MOSQUITOS?

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Open datasets
can be misused.

What about
other Gender
apart from
Male and female?

It can
be used
a wrong
way!!

This is true of
closed data, too.

YES
BIAS

OPEN DATASETS
CAN HELP US
BUILD MORE
RESPONSIBLE SOCIETIES
AND ACHIEVE
GOOD HEALTH
AND WELL-BEING.

OPEN DATASETS
ARE OFTEN
IMBALANCED,
PREDOMINANTLY
MALE AND WHITE.

It can be
very dangerous
if it goes in
a wrong
hand

Health data
is super
personal!

It risks
mislabeling what
we want to see
out in the world
sample

Greatly points

Can also
be used for
evil.

But we sort of
control what
we release
instruments!

Greatly. I
wonder
if we
can do
it to.

Well-being
is very
subjective.

Who defines
what is a
responsible
model? gov?
research
society?

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